

THE CYNAINNE DYES OF THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART VI

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2:6-Dimethylpyridine methiodide and 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine methiodide have been condensed with *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehydes, and the chemical, dyeing and photographic properties of the resulting compounds investigated. The influence of multiplication of *p*-dialkylamino residues on the sensitising power of certain cyanine dyes has been examined.

Mills and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 946) prepared the photographic sensitiser having the constitutional formula (S)

and it was found to have very useful photo-sensitising properties. The effect of change of the alkyl radical attached to the tertiary and quaternary nitrogen atoms, and the acid radicals, on the photographic characteristics of the compound, has been studied in this laboratory and reported in previous papers (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 347; Doja and Prasad, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 125; *idem.*, 377; *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 177). The influences of the change in the position of attachment of the *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde residue to the pyridine ring has also been reported (Doja and Prasad, *ibid.*, 1947, 24, 301). Bloch and Hamer (*Phot. J.*, 1930, 54, 374) have studied the effect of introducing two *p*-dimethylaminostyryl residues (I) in a quinaldine nucleus and have compared the sensitisation of this dye with that containing only one *p*-dimethylaminostyryl residue (II).

They have found that the sensitising effect of (I) is not superior to that of (II). In fact, the relative speed of (II) is greater than that of (I).

It was thus of interest to investigate the effect of introducing more than one *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde residues into the mononuclear (pyridine) class of cyanine dyes. For this purpose, 2:6-dimethylpyridine methyl iodide and 2:4:6-trimethylpyridine methyl iodide have been condensed with *p*-dimethyl- and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehydes and the resulting dyestuffs examined. In this way two sets of two compounds ('M' and 'N') and ('E' and 'F') have been prepared. The first set, 'M' and 'N' has been obtained by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with 2:4:6-trimethyl- and 2:6-dimethylpyridine methyl iodide and the second set, 'E' and 'F', by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with the same two pyridine derivatives, respectively. Table I shows some of the important properties of these compounds.

It is remarkable that both the dimethylamino compounds ('M' and 'N') have higher melting points than the corresponding diethylamino derivatives ('E' and 'F'). The yields of the products in the case of 'N' and 'F' are satisfactory but in the other two cases, they are comparatively poor. The yields of the crude products in all cases were good but they fell after recrystallisation.

Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.*, 1920, **55**, 255) observed that solutions of carbocyanines were decolorised by acidification with mineral acids. The dyestuffs under discussion further confirm the above observation, as their alcoholic solutions are decolorised by the addition of mineral acids. The "relative resistance to decolorisation" shown in Table I, has been determined by finding the value of *N*/100-HCl solution required to decolorise 2 c.c. of 1/100,000 solution of the dyes, and dividing the figures thus obtained by the smallest among these. Thus, it is seen that the dimethylamino dyes are more resistant to decolorisation than the diethylamino dyes.

It is also noteworthy that both the tri-styryl derivatives are dull-coloured powders, whereas the di-styryl derivatives form extremely beautiful shining crystals. All these compounds are soluble in acetic acid, chloroform and nitrobenzene. 'E' and 'F' are freely soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols but 'M' and 'N' dissolve only moderately in these solvents. All the four dyes are sparingly soluble in benzene and ligroin, and insoluble in water and petroleum ether.

Both the dimethyl- and the diethylamino compounds form ruby-red solutions, the latter giving a deeper shade. The "relative intensity" of colour in alcoholic solutions

TABLE I

Compound.	Colour and shape of crystals.	M.p.	Yield.	Reflex.	Pleochroism, one position.	Pleochroism, \perp position.	Relative resistance to decolorisation in alcoholic solution.	Relative intensity of colour in solution.	Extra sensitisation Ranges. Maximum.
M	Greenish grey powder	234°	37.4%	Nil	Yellowish grey (weak)	Bright yellow	4.65	1.64	5100-5800Å At about 5300Å
N	Shining green rhombs	254°	51.7	Strong yellowish green	Light grass green	Orange red	2.06	1.00	5100-6400 5400
E	Grey powder	202°	25.0	Nil	Yellowish white	Nearly opaque	1.40	1.79	At about 5100-5600 5400
F	Dirty green crystals	232°	74.06	Strong bottle green	Dirty white	Cherry red	1.00	2.12	5100-6500 5800

M = 2:4:6-Tri-(*p*-dimethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide.

N = 2:6-Di-(*p*-dimethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide.

E = 2:4:6-Tri-(*p*-diethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide.

F = 2:6-Di-(*p*-diethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide.

Unbathed plate.

Sensitisation.

} M

Absorption.

} N

} E

} F

(1/10,000) determined in the usual way, by means of a Duboscq colorimeter is given in Table I. The diethylamino compounds, as also visually seen, have a higher intensity value.

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (1/100,000) of these dyes is given in Table II (cf. Doja, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE II

Wallace colour filter No.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam.			
	M.	N.	E.	F.
1	Rose-red	Dull yellow	Weak yellow	Dull yellow
2	Faint pink	Pink	Weak red	Weak red
3	Cherry-red	Weak yellow	Claret-red	Reddish yellow
4	Crimson red	Reddish yellow	Cherry-red	Pink
5	Rose-red	Reddish yellow	Ruby-red	Yellowish red
6	Ruby-red	Greenish yellow	Yellowish red	Orange
7	Lemon-yellow	Yellow	Reddish yellow	Lemon-yellow
8	Dull yellow	Grass green	Light absorbed	Claret-red
9	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Very weak red	Yellowish pink
10	Crimson-red	Reddish yellow	Ruby-red	Yellowish red

The colour produced on silk, wool and cotton, when dyed with these compounds, is shown in Table III. They are not useful as dyestuffs. Neither the shades are good, nor are they fast either to sunlight or to washing.

The absorption spectra of alcoholic solutions (1/1000) of these dyestuffs taken in a Wedge-spectrograph are shown in Figure 1. They are characteristic of this class of compounds.

TABLE III

Compound.	Colour produced on		
	Silk.	Wool.	Cotton.
M	Weak yellowish blue	Mauve	Weak bluish red
N	Saffron	Dirty magenta	Weak magenta
E	Weak brinjal blue	Weak mauve	Reddish blue
F	Weak orange-yellow	Orange-yellow	Dull yellow

The sensitisation spectra are also shown in the same figure. They demonstrate that the multiplication of dialkylamino residues in a cyanine dye does not necessarily increase the sensitising power of the dyes. In the case under consideration, distyryl derivatives are better sensitisers than their tristyryl analogues (cf. Block and Hamer, *loc. cit.*). Salient features of the sensitisation spectra are given in Table I.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2:4:6-Trimethylpyridine methiodide.—2:4:6-Trimethylpyridine, prepared by the method of Hantzsch (*Annalen*, 1882, 216, 1), was quaternised with methyl iodide in a sealed tube by heating on a water-bath for 4 hours. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 205°. (Found: I, 48.18. $C_9H_{14}NI$ requires I, 48.29 per cent).

2:4:6-Tri-(*p*-dimethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide (M).—2:4:6-Trimethylpyridine methyl iodide (0.526 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.894 g.), piperidine (8 drops) and absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) were heated to a brisk boil under reflux on a water-bath for 12 hours. The reaction mixture developed a light orange colour in the cold; on heating the colour deepened and solid began to separate out. On cooling, the mother-liquor was filtered off and the residue crystallised four times from methyl alcohol, yield 0.49 g. (Found: N, 8.4; I, 19.29. $C_{36}H_{41}N_4I$ requires N, 8.53, I, 19.23 per cent).

2:4:6-Tri-(*p*-diethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide (E).—2:4:6-Trimethylpyridine methyl iodide (0.526 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.026 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (8 drops) were refluxed together for 12 hours. No solid separated out; only a pasty mass was obtained. It was kept in a refrigerator for 48 hours. The paste was scratched vigorously with a glass rod, when it solidified. The solid was recrystallised 4 times from methyl alcohol, yield 0.37 g. (Found: N, 7.57; I, 17.10. $C_{42}H_{55}N_4I$ requires N, 7.56; I, 17.16 per cent).

2:6-Dimethylpyridine methyl iodide.—2:6-Lutidine (10.7 g.) and methyl iodide (14.2 g.) were taken in a sealed tube and heated on the water-bath for 4 hours, and the solid thus obtained was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 16.2 g. (Found: I, 50.89. $C_8H_{12}NI$ requires I, 51.0 per cent).

2:6-Di-(*p*-dimethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide, (N).—2:6-Lutidine methyl iodide (1.245 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.49 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (5 drops) were heated briskly for 12 hours. The solid which separated out was recrystallised twice from nitrobenzene, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 8.12; I, 24.78. $C_{28}H_{30}N_3I$ requires N, 8.21; I, 24.85 per cent).

2:6-Di-(*p*-diethylamino)-styryl-pyridine methyl iodide, (F).—2:6-Lutidine methiodide (1.245 g.) *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.770 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (5 drops) were boiled under reflux on a water-bath for 12 hours. The mother-liquor was filtered off and the dye crystallised twice from pure methyl alcohol, yield 2.1 g. (Found: N, 7.32; I, 22.31. $C_{30}H_{38}N_3I$ requires N, 7.40; I, 22.40 per cent).